

**MEASURES TO SAVE ELECTRICAL ENERGY IN STATIC AND
DYNAMIC MODES OF ASYNCHRONOUS MOTORS USED IN
AGRICULTURE**

Panoyev A.T.

Doctor of Philosophy in Technical Sciences, Associate Professor. Head of the Department of "Electric Power Engineering and Electrical Engineering". National Research University "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers" Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management.

Bozorov M.B.

PhD, docent. Bukhara Engineering-Technological Institute.

Ahmadov E.K.

magister. Bukhara Engineering-Technological Institute.

Currently, asynchronous electric motors are the main consumers of electricity in agricultural enterprises. In agricultural enterprises, losses in the domestic electricity supply of the shop make up 9-10%, of which 12-15% are spent in the shop networks, and 85% in asynchronous motors (AM). Energy consumption in asynchronous motors used in agriculture is distributed in the following percentage. 43.6% of the energy consumption in an asynchronous motor is in the stator winding, 12.7% in the rotor winding, and 43.7% in the magnetic system of the motor [1,2,3,4]. Thus, the energy consumption of asynchronous electric motors is equal to the total consumption of electricity transmission and distribution. Therefore, measures to save electricity in asynchronous motors planned on the scale of agricultural enterprises will have a great economic effect. These measures include, first of all, measures related to the replacement of elements of the power supply system. In addition, replacement of under-loaded asynchronous motors, replacement of low-FIK equipment with modern efficient equipment, change of network voltage, compensation of reactive power are included. Reducing electrical energy waste can also be achieved by improving the

quality of electrical equipment repair[5,6,7,8]. This measure is especially effective in repairing asynchronous motors. In this case, after repair, the parameters of the asynchronous motor should be brought closer to the passport parameters. Poorly maintained asynchronous motors cause a lot of waste due to high consumption of reactive power, unsymmetrical windings, and excess current. Such negative situations require additional calculations when winding the winding of an asynchronous motor from its nominal values to other values (when the nominal speed, voltage, frequency changes). But, most of the time, the sample is repackaged with the data given in the tables. These measures include, first of all, measures related to the replacement of electrical equipment of technological machines that do not meet energy efficiency requirements. If the asynchronous motors used in agricultural enterprises are under-loaded, these include replacement of asynchronous motors, replacement of low-FIK equipment with modern efficient equipment, compensation of reactive power. the sample is repackaged with the information given in the tables[9,10,11,12]. These measures include, first of all, measures related to the replacement of electrical equipment of technological machines that do not meet energy efficiency requirements. If the asynchronous motors used in agricultural enterprises are under-loaded, these include replacement of asynchronous motors, replacement of low-FIK equipment with modern efficient equipment, compensation of reactive power. the sample is repackaged with the information given in the tables. These measures include, first of all, measures related to the replacement of electrical equipment of technological machines that do not meet energy efficiency requirements. If the asynchronous motors used in agricultural enterprises are under-loaded, these include replacement of asynchronous motors, replacement of low-FIK equipment with modern efficient equipment, compensation of reactive power[13,14].

The reduction in relative energy consumption of asynchronous motors used in agricultural enterprises is determined by b .

In this case, the determining coefficients b are determined based on the following formula.

$$\beta = \frac{k_n \cdot k_m + \alpha(1 - \eta_{MH})}{1 + \alpha(1 - \eta_{MH})k_u \cdot k_m}; \quad (1)$$

Here, k_n is the load coefficient, k_t is the coefficient of use of the asynchronous motor, α is the coefficient depending on the design of the asynchronous motor $\alpha=0.7-0.9$

ϵ_{mn} - nominal FIK of asynchronous motor;

k_t -coefficient is determined from the following expression.

$$k_t = T_m / (T_m + T_0),$$

T_m and T_0 are the working and idle time of the asynchronous motor.

Fig.1- In the picture -4A100L6U3The construction structure of a closed asynchronous motor with a short-circuited rotor is presented

1- frame, 2 - rim-bolt, 3 - stator core, 4 - rotor core, 5 - outer shell (housing), 6 and 10 - bearing caps, 7 - fan, 8 - balancing bags, 9 and 13 - bearings, 11 – rotor shaft, 12 – key, 14 – ventilation paddle, 15 – short connecting ring, 16 – screw

The less the asynchronous motor is loaded, the more the losses caused by the reactive power of the asynchronous motors used in agricultural enterprises.

An example.If we analyze the loads of an asynchronous motor with power $R=5.5$ kW and rotation speed $n=1000$ rev/min used in agricultural enterprises.

1. The load of the asynchronous motor is equal to $\cos \varphi=0.8$ at 100% load;
2. The load of the asynchronous motor is equal to 50% load $\cos \varphi=0.65$;
3. The load of the asynchronous motor is 30% load, $\cos \varphi=0.51$.

As a result of experimental studies, it was found that every 1 kVar of reactive power causes 1% to 15% of active power wastage. The reduction of electrical energy waste in agricultural enterprises can also be achieved by improving the quality of electrical equipment repair. This event is especially effective in repairing asynchronous motors. In this case, after repair, the parameters of the asynchronous motor should be brought closer to the passport parameters. Asynchronous motors used in agricultural enterprises cause a lot of waste due to the high consumption of reactive power, unsymmetrical windings, and excessive operating current.

REFERENCES

1. N.N. Sadullaev., A.Kh. Shoboev., M.B. Bozorov., A.T. Panoev. Sistema monitoringa elektropotrebleniy predpriyatiya na osnoe koeffitsienta effektivnosti sistemy elektrosnabzheniya. Europaische Fachhochschule. Volume: 08 / 2016. P.40-43. URL:<https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=27542999>e- ISSN: 2195-2183
2. N.N. Sadullaev., A.Kh. Shoboev., M.B. Bozorov., A.T. Panoev. Evaluation of the effectiveness of the system of electrical supply by the method of mnogokriterialnogo analysis. Europaische Fachhochschule. Volume: 08 / 2016. P.36-39. URL:<https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=27542998>e- ISSN: 2195-2183
3. Садуллаев Н. Н., Бозоров М. Б., Нематов Ш. Н. КОНТРОЛЬ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОЙ СЕТИ ПО ОБОБЩЕННОМУ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЮ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СИСТЕМЫ ЭЛЕКТРОСНАБЖЕНИЯ //3. 2018. – 1992. – С. 57. URL:<https://assets.uzsci.uz/edition/file/5e43dd733cce7.pdf#page=57>
4. MB BOZOROV., II KHAFIZOV., JM ZOIROV., FR KAYIMOV., BS KHAMDAMOV., D.A. ORIPOV., SHARIPOV A.SH. Forecasting electricity consumption of industrial enterprises using excel program. JournalNX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal. Volume: 07 ISSUE 2 / 2021. P.346-350. URL:<https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/342773-forecasting-electricity-consumption-of-i-ab0342bf.pdf>e- ISSN: 2581-4230

5. Kh. I. Hafizov., M.B. Bozorov. Razrabotka metoda kompleksnogo issledovaniya energoeffektivnosti sistemy elektrosnabzheniya promyshlennykh predpriyati. Sbornik statey Mejdunarodnogo nauchno-issledovatel'skogo konkursa. Petrazavodsk, Russia (2021). P. 10-19. URL: <http://is.nkzu.kz/publishings/%7BC1D6204A-6585-4F17-B6ADE67180342C1C%7D.pdf#page=12>
6. M.B. Bozorov., I.I. Hafizov., A.T. Panoev., J.M. Zoirov., Sh.K. Ergashev., F.R. Kayimov., B.S. Khamdamov., D.A. Oripov., A.Sh. Sharipov. Razrabotka metoda otsenki effektivnosti sistemy elektrosnabzheniya promyshlennykh predpriyatiy. Sbornik nauchnykh statey po itogam mejdunarodnoy nauchnoy conference. Kazan (2021). P. 42-45. URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=44776698>
7. Bozorov M. B. ISSLEDOVANIYA ENERGOEFFEKTIVNOSTI SISTEMY ELEKTROSNABJENIYA OB'EKTOV ENERGOSSISTEM NA OSNOVE OBOBshchENNYX POKAZATELEY EFFEKTIVNOSTI //Rossiyskaya nauka v sovremennom mire. - 2018. - S. 69-71. URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=36354438>
8. Sadullayev NN, Bozorov MB, Nematov Sh N. Research of Efficiency of Functioning of System of Electro Supply of the Enterprise by Method Multi-Criteria Analysis //Journal of Electrical & Electronic Systems. - 2018. - T. 7. – no. 2. - S. 18-20. URL: <https://www.hilarispublisher.com/open-access/research-of-efficiency-of-functioning-of-system-of-electro-supply-of-the-enterprise-by-method-multicriteria-analysis-2332-0796-1000257.pdf>
9. Sadullaev N. N., Shoboev A. Kh., Bozorov M. B. ISSLEDOVANIE VLIYANIYa REGULIROVANYa PARAMETROVELEKTROENERGII NA VYBOR OPTIMALNOY SCHEMY ELEKTROSNABJENIYa //Sovremennye instrumentalnye sistemy, informatsionnye tehnologii i innovatsii. - 2014. - S. 28-32. URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=22546679>

10. Bozorov M. B. et al. USE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES FOR LOW-POWER ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN //British View. – 2022. – T. 7. – №. 3. URL: <https://britishview.co.uk/index.php/bv/article/view/120>
11. Bakhshiloevich B. M. et al. Development of A Method for A Comprehensive Study of the Efficiency of the Power Supply System of Industrial Enterprises //Open Access Repository. – 2022. – T. 8. – №. 04. – C. 71-77. URL: <https://oarepo.org/index.php/oa/article/view/553>
12. Bakhshiloevich B. M., Rasulovich Q. F., Akmalovich O. D. Development of a combined method for forecasting electricity consumption of an industrial enterprise llc evrosnar //World Bulletin of Social Sciences. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 57-64. URL: <https://www.scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbss/article/view/715>
13. Panoev, Abdullo, and Makhsun Bozorov. "Compensation of Reactive Power in Asynchronous Motors of Agricultural Enterprises." Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology 16 (2023): 8-14. URL: <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejet/article/view/3568>
14. Panoev, Abdullo, and Makhsun Bozorov. "ACHIEVING ENERGY SAVING BY COVERING THE REACTIVE POWER IN THE OPERATION OF ASYNCHRONOUS MOTORS USED IN AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES." (2023). URL: <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/ejare/article/view/3378>